

Evaluating Radiation Characteristics of Cr-Coated Silicon Carbide and Zircaloy Claddings in a PWR Fuel Assembly: A Simulation Study Employing GEANT4 and EpiXS

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Abstract: Nuclear fuel cladding materials act as protective barriers for UO_2 pellets, providing essential corrosion resistance and maintaining low neutron and gamma radiation absorption cross-sections. To enhance the accident-tolerant fuel (ATF) framework and strengthen nuclear fuel cladding protection, this study investigates chromium-coated Zirconium alloy (E110) and Silicon Carbide (SiC) as cladding materials in a PWR reactor fuel assembly. The key concern addressed is the degradation of the irradiated inner and outer cladding surface, driven by fission fragments produced during nuclear reactions, steam with high temperature, and the formation of hydrides. SiC demonstrates superior resistance to chemical attacks compared to Zircaloy, oxidizes less aggressively at high temperatures, has a higher yield strength, and shows a significantly lower creep rate and neutron capture cross-section. However, the application of a chromium coating can influence the radiation response of both materials. The study aims to determine the suitable nuclear fuel cladding between Zircaloy and Silicon Carbide with Cr coating. The performance of Zircaloy (E110) and SiC cladding materials with thin chromium coatings is modeled and assessed in this work using GEANT4 simulation software. The outcomes are verified and compared to the EpiXS software dataset to guarantee precision and dependability. For modeling radiation interactions and material deterioration, GEANT4 provides a sizable dataset. These discoveries aid in creating stronger cladding materials, which raise nuclear reactor efficiency and safety. The work also shows how GEANT4 can precisely evaluate the radiation characteristics of materials exposed to gamma and neutron radiation, providing vital data for improving cladding performance in radiation environments and raising nuclear safety requirements.

Key-Words: UO_2 , Accident-Tolerant Fuel (ATF), Zirconium Alloy (E110), Silicon Carbide (SiC), Chromium (Cr), Geant4, EpiXS, Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR).

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1 Introduction

The cladding material in nuclear fuel rods serves as a shield for UO_2 , and in order to reduce neutron capture, it should ideally have a low absorption cross-section. Important characteristics including high-temperature stability, robust corrosion resistance, and low absorption cross-section are crucial for selecting cladding materials for accident-tolerant fuel cladding. Zircaloy and other zirconium-based alloys are frequently utilized as cladding in light water reactors. good-temperature circumstances are especially advantageous for cladding materials with good oxidation resistance. Silicon carbide (SiC) is a better choice than zircaloy because of its lower absorption cross-section [1].

Fuel cladding's irradiation internal surface has not undergone as much research on oxidation and

degradation as its external surface. This degradation has been closely associated with the presence of fission fragments generated during nuclear fuel fission. To enhance durability, corrosion-resistant, Cr coatings are applied to both Zircaloy and SiC cladding materials in this study, allowing for a comparative evaluation of performance on the inner and outer cladding surfaces. Although Cr has a relatively high neutron cross-section, both Zircaloy and SiC have low absorption cross-sections, making them effective choices for cladding materials [2].

Even though Zircaloy performs well as a cladding material, it has chemical damage, degradation of mechanical strength, and chemical properties at high temperatures. Also, it reacts with oxygen and becomes corrosive. Because of hydrides, it loses its property of ductility [3].

Silicon Carbide (SiC), on the other hand, demonstrates greater resilience under high temperatures and shows superior resistance to chemical attack, oxidation, and creep, making it highly advantageous in accident-tolerant fuel cladding applications. Its lower neutron absorption cross-section, compared to Zircaloy, further enhances its suitability by minimizing radiation-induced degradation over time [4]. This study's insights into SiC and Zircaloy, with Cr coating, contribute to optimizing cladding material selection for improved performance in nuclear reactors. Using SiC as cladding presents some challenges, such as its relatively low thermal conductivity after irradiation and the possibility of large stresses that could affect structural integrity [5]. Nonetheless, the high oxidation resistance and strength of SiC in high-temperature steam environments make it an attractive option for exploring accident-tolerant fuel (ATF) designs [6].

This study examines mass attenuation coefficient, HVL, effective atomic number, and effective electron density for both materials to identify which offers better cladding performance. Zircaloy performs well under typical reactor core conditions; however, it is prone to oxidation, forming a surface layer that contributes to corrosion. Furthermore, its tendency to absorb hydrogen results in hydrides formation, reducing ductility. To address these issues, Cr coating is applied to both inner and outer surfaces. Various deposition techniques have been employed, including physical vapor deposition (PVD) by CEA in France, Chemical vapor deposition (CVD), vacuum arc ion-plasma technology in Russia, and 3D laser technology, cold spraying, and arc ion plating in Korea [7]. Research has demonstrated that applying a thin metallic chromium film significantly enhances corrosion resistance in both Zircaloy and Silicon Carbide.

Researchers have examined the thermal-hydraulic and neutronic properties of Zircaloy and SiC as cladding materials in nuclear applications. By investigating the radiation characteristics of Cr-coated Zircaloy and SiC using Geant4, which allows for intricate simulations of particle interactions and radiation transport, this work presents a novel methodology. A strong framework for assessing how these materials behave under different radiation situations is offered by Geant4 [8][9][10][11]. To ensure a precise and comprehensive investigation of radiation shielding performance, the simulation findings are further confirmed using EpiXS [12]. In order to increase nuclear reactor safety and

efficiency, this effort attempts to provide insightful information about the best cladding material selection.

2 Materials

Zircaloy is widely used as a cladding material in nuclear reactors due to its low neutron absorption cross-section. In contrast, Silicon Carbide (SiC) also has a low absorption cross-section and offers superior mechanical properties compared to Zircaloy (E110), making it a strong candidate for advanced cladding applications [13]. Ongoing research is focused on exploring new materials for cladding in fuel rods to improve performance under reactor conditions. In this study, Zircaloy (E110) and Silicon Carbide (SiC) are both investigated with Cr coatings applied to their inner and outer surfaces [14]. Chromium coating is well-known for improving corrosion resistance and durability and can be applied using a variety of methods [15]. In this research, the single-crystal chemical vapor deposition (scCVD) technique is employed in the simulation for Cr coating [16]. Table 1 provides a summary of the chemical composition of both materials, outlining their elemental content and reinforcing their potential use in accident-tolerant fuel applications.

Table 1. Chemical Composition of Candidate materials [1][2][3][4][5][6][7]

Cladding materials with their elemental composition weight (%)										
Materials	Density	Thickness (cm)	Nb	Sn	Fe	O	Zr	Si	C	Cr
Zircaloy (E110)	6.56	2.048cm	0.9	1.1	0.3	0.06	97.64			
SiC	2.6	2.048cm						70.8	29.92	
Cr	7.192	9µm								100

3 Theory

The mass attenuation coefficient is related to gamma energy, density, and Z_{eff} of material, and it is

a fundamental property of the shielding capabilities of any material [17]. HVL is defined as the inverse proportion of the attenuation coefficient. It represents the thickness of a material required to reduce the intensity of initial gamma radiation energy by half [17]. The effective atomic number (Z_{eff}) represents the overall atomic number of composite materials during gamma radiation interactions [18]. The effective electron density (N_{eff}) is a parameter of gamma radiation that refers to the average number of electrons per unit mass, determining how gamma rays interact with the material [18].

Gamma radiation intensity follows Beer-Lambert's law, as shown in Equation (1) [19][20][21][22][23].

$$I = I_0 e^{-\mu(E)t} \quad (1)$$

Here, I_0 and I represent the unattenuated and attenuated intensities of the gamma radiation beam, respectively. $\mu(E)$ (cm^{-1}) is the material's linear attenuation coefficient at the particular E, and t (cm) denotes the thickness of the absorbing sample.

The gamma mass attenuation coefficient (μ_m) is determined using Equation (2) [19][20][21][22][23].

$$I = I_0 e^{-\left\{\frac{\mu(E)}{\rho}\right\}t_d} = I_0 e^{-\mu_m(E)t_d} \quad (2)$$

Here, I_0 and I are the unattenuated and attenuated gamma intensities, $\mu_m = \mu/\rho$ (cm^2/g) is the mass attenuation coefficient, and t_d (g/cm^2) represents the density thickness of the absorber. Equation (3) calculates mass attenuation at a given energy [19][20][21][22][23].

$$\mu_m(E) = \frac{\mu(E)}{\rho} = \frac{1}{\rho t} \ln\left(\frac{I_0}{I}\right) = \frac{1}{t_d} \ln\left(\frac{I_0}{I}\right) \quad (3)$$

Equation (4) illustrates the relationship between t and t_d [19][20][21][22][23].

$$t_d = \rho \times t \quad (4)$$

Equation (5) defines the relationship between μ and μ_m [19][20][21][22][23].

$$\mu_m = \frac{\mu}{\rho} \quad (5)$$

For any chemical compound or mixture of elements, the total mass attenuation coefficient $(\mu/\rho)_{\text{compound or mixture}}$ is defined by the mixture rule, as shown in Equation (6) [19][20][21][22][23].

$$(\mu/\rho)_{\text{compound}} = \sum_i (\mu/\rho)_i w_i \quad (6)$$

Here, w_i and (μ/ρ) represent the weight fraction and mass attenuation coefficient of the i th constituent element, respectively. For a chemical compound, the weight fraction (w_i) is defined by Equation (7)[19][20][21][22][23].

$$w_i = \frac{n_i A_i}{\sum_i n_i A_i} \quad (7)$$

Here, A_i denotes the atomic weight of the i th element, n_i indicates the number of formula units, and it is important to note that $\sum_i w_i = 1$.

The total linear attenuation coefficient $\mu_{\text{compound or mixture}}$, can be calculated by simply multiplying the total mass attenuation coefficient $(\mu/\rho)_{\text{compound}}$ by its density, ρ as specified in Equation (8) [19][20][21][22][23].

$$\mu_{\text{compound}} = \left(\frac{\mu}{\rho}\right)_{\text{compound}} \times \rho \quad (8)$$

The thickness of a shield or absorber that decreases the radiation level by half of its original value is known as the Half Value Layer (HVL) and is determined using Equation (9) [19][20][21][22][23].

$$HVL = \frac{\ln(2)}{\mu} = \frac{0.693}{\mu} \quad (9)$$

The total molecular cross-section can be calculated by applying Equation (10) [19][20][21][22][23].

$$\sigma_{t,m} = \left(\frac{\mu}{\rho}\right) \frac{A_t}{N_A} = \frac{1}{N_A} \left(\frac{\mu}{\rho}\right) \sum_i n_i A_i \quad (10)$$

Furthermore, Equation (11) provides the calculation for the total atomic cross-section [19][20][21][22][23].

$$\sigma_{t,a} = \sigma_{t,m} \frac{1}{\sum_i n_i} = \frac{\sigma_{t,m}}{\sum n_i} \quad (11)$$

Here, (N_A) represents Avogadro's number, ($A_t = \sum n_i A_i$) denotes the molecular weight, (A_i) is the atomic weight of an element within the compound, and (n_i) is the total number of atoms. The total electronic cross-section for the element is provided in Equation (12) [19][20][21][22][23].

$$\sigma_{t,e} = \frac{1}{N_A} \sum_i^n \frac{f_i A_i}{Z_i} (\mu_m)_i = \frac{1}{N_A} \sum_i f_i \frac{A_i}{Z_i} \left(\frac{\mu}{\rho}\right)_i \quad (12)$$

Here, (f_i) represents the number of atoms of element (i) relative to the total number of atoms of all elements in the compound, and (Z_i) is the atomic number of the i th element in the compound. The effective atomic number (Z_{eff}) of the compound can be determined by the ratio of the total atomic cross-section to the total electronic cross-section, as given by Equation (13) [19][20][21][22][23].

$$Z_{eff} = \frac{\sigma_{t,a}}{\sigma_{t,e}} \quad (13)$$

The effective electron density, denoted as (N_{eff}), is given by Equation (14) [19][20][21][22][23].

$$N_{eff} = \frac{\mu_m}{\sigma_{t,e}} = \frac{\left(\frac{\mu}{\rho}\right)_c}{\sigma_{te}} = \frac{N_A n_{tot} Z_{eff}}{\sum_i n_i A_i} \quad (14)$$

Here, $(\mu/\rho)_c$ represents the compound's mass attenuation coefficient, and σ_{te} denotes the total electronic cross-section.

4 Methodology

This study investigates the radiation characteristics of chromium-coated Zircaloy (E110) and Silicon Carbide (SiC) as cladding materials for nuclear fuel rods in a Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR). The research employs a Monte Carlo-based simulation approach using the GEANT4 toolkit, widely utilized in nuclear physics, engineering, and medical applications. Geant4 was specifically employed to evaluate gamma radiation and neutron-shielding properties by modeling particle interactions with the materials under investigation [8][9][10][11].

The methodology begins with the selection of Zircaloy (E110) and Silicon Carbide (SiC) based on their potential as accident-tolerant fuel (ATF) claddings. Both materials were coated with Chromium (Cr) to enhance their corrosion resistance and durability under high-temperature and radiation exposure conditions. A source emitting mono-energetic gamma radiation within the energy range of 0.1 MeV to 20 MeV was directed at the samples, followed by a detector to measure attenuation. The

attenuation characteristics were determined by evaluating the ratio of particles reaching the detector with and without the sample. Key parameters analyzed include the mass attenuation coefficient (μ_m), half-value layer (HVL), effective atomic number (Z_{eff}), and effective electron density (N_{eff}), all of which describe the material's shielding efficiency and radiation interaction properties.

EpiXS software was employed to validate the computational results. EpiXS, based on EPICS2017 and EPDL97 libraries, provides a user-friendly platform for photon attenuation and shielding analysis. The results from GEANT4 simulations were cross-verified with EpiXS outputs, and percentage deviations were calculated to ensure accuracy. Deviations within 1.5% were considered acceptable, demonstrating the reliability of the methodology [12].

The simulations utilized Python's Matplotlib library for plotting and analyzing results, providing visual insights into shielding properties. Chromium coatings were modeled using the Single-Crystal Chemical Vapor Deposition (scCVD) technique to replicate realistic coating applications. The results were analyzed to compare shielding efficiency, thermal stability, and long-term performance under radiation exposure, offering insights into potential degradation mechanisms [16][24].

This methodology establishes a comprehensive framework for evaluating advanced cladding materials and highlights their suitability for improving nuclear reactor safety and efficiency. Additionally, the results were compared against experimental datasets, ensuring practical relevance and consistency with existing literature.

5 Result

5.1 Gamma radiation shielding of Cr-coated Zircaloy and Silicon Carbide (SiC)

The gamma radiation shielding properties of Cr-coated Zircaloy and SiC have been analyzed across a broad energy range from 0.1MeV to 20 MeV and compared with the obtained EpiXS result using

Equation (15) to evaluate the Geant4 result. EpiXS is based on the EPICS2017 of ENDF/B-VIII and EPDL97 of ENDF/B-VI.8 and it is a Windows-based application for photon/gamma radiation attenuation, dosimetry, and shielding, offering photon cross-section data for any sample [12]. Matplotlib software is used to plot the graphs of mass attenuation coefficient, HVL, effective atomic number (Z_{eff}) and effective electron density (N_{eff}) in the studied energy range [24].

$$\Delta\% = \left(\frac{\text{EpiXS Result} - \text{Geant4 Result}}{\text{EpiXS Result}} \right) \times 100 \quad (15)$$

With an average of 0.215% for Zircaloy and 0.037% for SiC across the entire energy range, the percentage discrepancies in mass attenuation coefficients were less than 1.5% for Zircaloy and less than 1% for SiC, demonstrating a high degree of consistency between the Geant4 and EpiXS results. Likewise, the average difference in HVLs estimate was 0.12% for Zircaloy and 0.048% for SiC, both being less than 1%. The effective atomic numbers for both cladding materials also showed good agreement, with average percentage discrepancies of 0.013% for Zircaloy and 0.009% for SiC. Additionally, the effective neutron densities yielded even better results, with average percentage discrepancies of 0.018% for Zircaloy and 0.015% for SiC. Although the differences were more noticeable at lower energies, they remained under 5%. These findings validate the reliability of the Geant4 code for determining a material's gamma radiation shielding characteristics.

Table 2. Displays the results and percentage changes in the mass attenuation coefficients of both cladding materials using Geant4 and EpiXS.

Energy (MeV)	Mass Attenuation Coefficient, μ_m (cm ² /g)					
	Zircaloy(E110)			SiC		
	EpiXS	Geant4	%Δ	EpiXS	Geant4	%Δ
0.1	0.975	0.973	0.20512821	0.1742	0.174175	0.01435132

0.15	0.382	0.381	0.2617801	0.14183	0.14094	0.62751181
0.2	0.225	0.223	0.88888889	0.126161	0.126109	0.04121717
0.25	0.163	0.164	-0.6134969	0.11563	0.11509	0.46700683
0.3	0.132	0.131	0.75757576	0.107673	0.107579	0.08730137
0.35	0.114	0.113	0.87719298	0.101192	0.101089	0.1017867
0.4	0.102	0.103	-0.9803922	0.0958754	0.095852	0.02440668
0.45	0.0934	0.0935	-0.1070664	0.0912488	0.0912375	0.01238372
0.5	0.0869	0.0871	-0.2301496	0.0873136	0.0872859	0.03172473
0.55	0.0817	0.0821	-0.4895961	0.0837745	0.0836759	0.11769691
0.6	0.0775	0.0781	-0.7741935	0.0806506	0.0805917	0.07303107
0.65	0.0739	0.0741	-0.270636	0.0778078	0.0777927	0.01940679
0.7	0.0708	0.0711	-0.4237288	0.0752336	0.0753193	-0.11391187
0.75	0.068	0.0691	-1.6176471	0.0728893	0.0727108	0.24489191
0.8	0.0656	0.0661	-0.7621951	0.070729	0.071039	-0.43829264
0.85	0.0634	0.0641	-1.1041009	0.0687062	0.0686019	0.15180581
0.9	0.0615	0.0621	-0.9756098	0.0668574	0.0669193	-0.09258511
0.95	0.0597	0.0589	1.3400335	0.0651545	0.0652068	-0.08027074
1	0.058	0.0579	0.17241379	0.0635313	0.0636902	-0.25011294
2	0.0414	0.0417	-0.7246377	0.0446	0.0449539	-0.79349776
3	0.0364	0.0359	1.37362637	0.0363704	0.0362691	0.27852319
4	0.0345	0.0339	1.73913043	0.0317469	0.0316193	0.40192901
5	0.0338	0.0341	-0.887574	0.0288321	0.0289204	-0.30625587
6	0.0337	0.0331	1.78041543	0.0268608	0.0267194	0.52641768
7	0.0339	0.0335	1.179941	0.0254506	0.0253905	0.23614375
8	0.0344	0.0339	1.45348837	0.0244348	0.0243049	0.53161884
9	0.0349	0.0348	0.28653295	0.0236608	0.0237294	-0.28993103
10	0.0355	0.0352	0.84507042	0.0230668	0.0231948	-0.55491009
11	0.0361	0.0359	0.55401662	0.0225949	0.0226139	-0.08408977
12	0.0367	0.0361	1.63487738	0.0222345	0.0221936	0.18394837
13	0.0374	0.0371	0.80213904	0.0219454	0.0218937	0.23558468
14	0.0379	0.0378	0.26385224	0.0217071	0.0217966	-0.41230749
15	0.0385	0.0386	-0.2597403	0.0215276	0.0214156	0.52026236
16	0.0391	0.0392	-0.2557545	0.0213861	0.0212136	0.80659868
17	0.0396	0.0389	1.76767677	0.0212592	0.0211149	0.67876496
18	0.0402	0.0405	-0.7462687	0.0211855	0.0212958	-0.52063912
19	0.0407	0.0403	0.98280098	0.0211091	0.0212039	-0.44909541
20	0.0412	0.0411	0.24271845	0.0210659	0.0211935	-0.60571825

Figure 1. The mass attenuation coefficients of Zircaloy cladding materials using Geant4 and EpiXS.

Figure 2. The mass attenuation coefficients of SiC cladding materials using Geant4 and EpiXS.

Figure 1 and 2 demonstrates the mass attenuation coefficients of Cr-coated Zircaloy and SiC across a gamma energy range (0.1 MeV to 20 MeV). SiC consistently shows lower values at high energies, signifying superior radiation transparency, crucial for reducing radiation-induced degradation. Zircaloy, with higher coefficients at lower energies, provides better low-energy gamma shielding but is prone to degradation over time.

Table 3. Displays the results and percentage changes in the HVLs of both cladding materials using Geant4 and EpiXS.

Energy (MeV)	Half-value layer (cm)					
	Zircaloy(E110)			SiC		
	EpiXS	Geant4	%Δ	EpiXS	Geant4	%Δ
0.1	0.108388	0.109289	0.831272835	1.5304	1.5274	0.196027182
0.15	0.276412	0.276195	0.078505998	1.87968	1.86928	0.553285666
0.2	0.46951	0.46869	0.174650167	2.11313	2.12177	0.408872147
0.25	0.647786	0.648612	0.127511246	2.3056	2.3178	0.529146426
0.3	0.799664	0.798545	0.139933772	2.47596	2.47902	0.123588426
0.35	0.927693	0.926734	0.103374716	2.63456	2.63394	0.023533341
0.4	1.03656	1.02975	0.656980783	2.78064	2.78158	0.033805167
0.45	1.13179	1.13045	0.118396522	2.92163	2.9169	0.161895928
0.5	1.21537	1.2146	0.063355192	3.05331	3.06014	0.223691666
0.55	1.29312	1.29212	0.077332343	3.18229	3.17036	0.374887267
0.6	1.36285	1.36167	0.086583263	3.30556	3.31048	0.148840136
0.65	1.4301	1.4298	0.020977554	3.42633	3.43051	0.121996422
0.7	1.49296	1.49189	0.071669703	3.54356	3.54249	0.030195622
0.75	1.55273	1.55151	0.078571291	3.65753	3.66931	-0.32207528
0.8	1.61009	1.61143	0.083225161	3.76925	3.75306	0.429528421
0.85	1.66572	1.65768	0.482674159	3.88022	3.89384	0.351011025
0.9	1.71904	1.71868	0.020941921	3.98752	3.97934	0.205140037
0.95	1.77043	1.76987	0.031630734	4.09174	4.08032	0.279098867
1	1.82119	1.81267	0.467825982	4.19628	4.18549	0.257132508
2	2.55289	2.53687	0.6275241	5.97747	5.96037	0.286074209
3	2.90406	2.91563	0.398407746	7.33	7.3259	0.055934516
4	3.06647	3.05796	0.277517797	8.39752	8.38305	0.172312778
5	3.12769	3.11792	0.312371111	9.24647	9.23058	0.171849365
6	3.13583	3.12789	0.253202501	9.92507	9.91059	0.145893178
7	3.11339	3.12186	0.272050723	10.475	10.465	0.095465394
8	3.07368	3.06798	0.18544546	10.9105	10.9005	0.091654828
9	3.02668	3.01835	0.275219052	11.2674	11.2593	0.071888812
10	2.97613	2.98519	0.304422186	11.5575	11.5563	0.010382868
11	2.92566	2.91648	0.313775353	11.7989	11.8039	0.042376832
12	2.87558	2.86487	0.372446602	11.9901	11.9849	0.043369113
13	2.82855	2.81954	0.318537767	12.1481	12.1361	0.098780879
14	2.7849	2.7778	0.254946318	12.2815	12.2749	0.053739364
15	2.74291	2.73879	0.150205439	12.3839	12.3719	0.096900007
16	2.70297	2.71087	0.292271094	12.4658	12.4596	0.049736078
17	2.66763	2.65897	0.324632726	12.5402	12.5495	0.074161497
18	2.63012	2.62789	0.084787006	12.5839	12.5719	0.095359944
19	2.59792	2.58987	0.309863275	12.6294	12.6147	0.116395078
20	2.56467	2.55981	0.189498064	12.6553	12.6493	0.047410966

Figure 3. The HVLs of Zircaloy cladding materials using Geant4 and EpiXS.

Figure 4. The HVLs of SiC cladding materials using Geant4 and EpiXS.

Figure 3 and 4 illustrates HVL values for both materials. While Zircaloy exhibits lower HVL across the spectrum, indicating higher attenuation capability, its high hydrogen absorption remains a significant drawback. SiC, with higher HVL, provides adequate shielding while maintaining structural integrity over prolonged exposure.

Table 4. Displays the results and percentage changes in the effective atomic number (Z_{eff}) of both cladding materials using Geant4 and EpiXS.

Energy (MeV)	Effective atomic number Z_{eff}					
	Zircaloy(E110)			SiC		
	EpiXS	Geant4	%Δ	EpiXS	Geant4	%Δ
0.1	40.11281	40.12034	-0.018782	10.41162	10.41285	-0.01181373
0.15	40.07017	40.08937	-0.0479334	10.1679	10.16648	0.013886845
0.2	40.02587	40.01925	0.01655429	10.09443	10.09594	-0.01493893
0.25	39.9906	39.98269	0.01977465	10.06386	10.07038	-0.06469682
0.3	39.96522	39.95394	0.02823705	10.04838	10.04576	0.026093756
0.35	39.94753	39.93945	0.02022653	10.03942	10.03573	0.036784986
0.4	39.93502	39.92685	0.02047326	10.03374	10.03249	0.012477903
0.45	39.92609	39.91937	0.0168336	10.03001	10.03946	-0.09418731
0.5	39.91958	39.90982	0.02444916	10.02753	10.02859	-0.0105709
0.55	39.91468	39.90695	0.01936881	10.02527	10.02396	0.013047035
0.6	39.91081	39.90196	0.02218196	10.02402	10.02236	0.016620072
0.65	39.90784	39.9191	-0.0282125	10.0228	10.02749	-0.04687315
0.7	39.90543	39.90106	0.0109534	10.02184	10.02054	0.01301158
0.75	39.90352	39.90851	-0.0125027	10.02103	10.01948	0.015397625
0.8	39.90191	39.89487	0.01764577	10.02037	10.02483	-0.04451932
0.85	39.90061	39.89479	0.01457121	10.01988	10.01836	0.015090009
0.9	39.89949	39.88985	0.02416071	10.01946	10.0183	0.011517591

0.95	39.89853	39.8851	0.03366039	10.01906	10.01743	0.016338852
1	39.89772	39.89165	0.0152139	10.01881	10.01729	0.015161477
2	39.89956	39.89387	0.01426833	10.03585	10.0345	0.013541448
3	39.9131	39.90807	0.0126099	10.08405	10.08596	-0.01901022
4	39.92668	39.92006	0.01659291	10.14219	10.14396	-0.01741241
5	39.93841	39.9309	0.01882148	10.20314	10.21045	-0.07163478
6	39.94803	39.94099	0.01763041	10.26352	10.26095	0.024962206
7	39.95611	39.95028	0.01457349	10.3216	10.31495	0.064437697
8	39.96278	39.95595	0.01710592	10.37647	10.37936	-0.02781293
9	39.96843	39.96158	0.01715104	10.42807	10.41945	0.082651903
10	39.97327	39.96608	0.01798702	10.47623	10.46986	0.060823424
11	39.97743	39.97108	0.01590397	10.52065	10.5303	-0.0916483
12	39.981	39.97453	0.01618269	10.56177	10.56355	-0.01684377
13	39.98412	39.97769	0.01608138	10.59992	10.60385	-0.03711349
14	39.98679	39.98075	0.01510999	10.63555	10.62953	0.056583805
15	39.98911	39.98291	0.01551422	10.66878	10.67295	-0.0390485
16	39.99112	39.98483	0.01573849	10.6991	10.70938	-0.09610157
17	39.9929	39.98704	0.0146651	10.72763	10.73057	-0.02740587
18	39.99451	39.98896	0.0138769	10.75466	10.75036	0.040001268
19	39.99595	39.99072	0.01308632	10.77932	10.7892	-0.09165695
20	39.99728	39.99146	0.01454349	10.80295	10.81045	-0.06943476

0.2	2.649622	2.649168	0.01713452	3.027309	3.026761	0.018101885
0.25	2.647287	2.646919	0.013901024	3.018143	3.017795	0.011530269
0.3	2.645607	2.644826	0.029520636	3.013499	3.012624	0.029036014
0.35	2.644436	2.643369	0.040348868	3.010812	3.011598	0.026105914
0.4	2.643608	2.642489	0.042328515	3.009108	3.008531	0.019175118
0.45	2.643017	2.64089	0.080476213	3.007991	3.008462	0.015658292
0.5	2.642585	2.643225	-0.02421871	3.007246	3.006922	0.010773977
0.55	2.642261	2.643304	0.039473769	3.006567	3.005984	0.019390887
0.6	2.642005	2.641042	0.03644959	3.006195	3.004329	0.062071822
0.65	2.641808	2.642904	0.041486739	3.005826	3.006135	0.010280036
0.7	2.641649	2.641265	0.014536375	3.00554	3.004778	0.025353181
0.75	2.641522	2.641034	0.018474198	3.005296	3.004675	0.020663522
0.8	2.641416	2.640956	0.017414902	3.005098	3.004164	0.031080517
0.85	2.64133	2.640876	0.01718831	3.00495	3.004518	0.014376279
0.9	2.641256	2.641001	0.009654498	3.004825	3.005176	0.011681213
0.95	2.641192	2.640469	0.027374004	3.004707	3.004168	0.017938521
1	2.641138	2.64057	0.021505881	3.004632	3.004121	0.017007074
2	2.64126	2.640905	0.013440555	3.009742	3.009176	0.018805599
3	2.642156	2.641662	0.018696852	3.024196	3.022563	0.053997823
4	2.643056	2.642674	0.014452967	3.041633	3.041164	0.015419349
5	2.643832	2.643408	0.016037328	3.059913	3.059431	0.015752082
6	2.644469	2.643971	0.018831758	3.078018	3.077434	0.018973248
7	2.645003	2.644636	0.013875221	3.095437	3.095045	0.012663802
8	2.645445	2.645007	0.016556761	3.111893	3.111475	0.013432338
9	2.645819	2.645309	0.019275695	3.127368	3.127008	0.011511277
10	2.646139	2.645701	0.016552418	3.14181	3.141271	0.017155716
11	2.646415	2.645976	0.016588479	3.155133	3.154572	0.01778055
12	2.646651	2.646143	0.019194068	3.167463	3.167105	0.011302421
13	2.646858	2.646419	0.016585703	3.178905	3.178446	0.014438934
14	2.647035	2.646568	0.017642381	3.189591	3.189073	0.016240327
15	2.647188	2.646774	0.015639237	3.199557	3.198914	0.020096532
16	2.647321	2.646947	0.01412749	3.208648	3.207873	0.024153475
17	2.647439	2.647064	0.014164632	3.217205	3.216876	0.010226268
18	2.647546	2.647164	0.014428456	3.225311	3.224899	0.012773962
19	2.647641	2.647276	0.013785857	3.232708	3.232322	0.011940454
20	2.647729	2.647319	0.015484968	3.239793	3.239046	0.023057029

Figure 5. Displays effective atomic numbers (Z_{eff}) of Zircaloy was determined using Geant4 and EpiXS.

Figure 6. Displays effective atomic numbers (Z_{eff}) of SiC was determined using Geant4 and EpiXS.

Table 5. shows the outcomes and percentage variations in the two cladding materials' effective electron density (N_{eff}) utilizing Geant4 and EpiXS.

Energy (MeV)	Effective electron density, N_{eff} ($\times 10^{23}$ electrons g^{-1})					
	Zircaloy(E110)			SiC		
	EpiXS	Geant4	%Δ	EpiXS	Geant4	%Δ
0.1	2.655377	2.653347	0.076448655	3.122434	3.121945	0.015660859
0.15	2.652554	2.651355	0.045201719	3.049342	3.048812	0.017380799

Figure 7. The effective electron densities (N_{eff}) of Zircaloy cladding materials using Geant4 and EpiXS.

Figure 8. The effective electron densities (N_{eff}) of SiC cladding materials using Geant4 and EpiXS.

6 Discussion

This study assesses the appropriateness of Cr-coated silicon carbide (SiC) and zircaloy as cladding materials in the energy range of 0.1 MeV to 20 MeV by evaluating the shielding performance of these materials against gamma radiation on both their inner and outer sides. Important gamma radiation characteristics for both materials are investigated, including mass attenuation, half-value layer (HVL), effective atomic number, and effective electron density. Cr-coated Zircaloy and Cr-coated SiC are both examined as potential cladding materials for nuclear fuel rods. Since low radiation energy absorption is advantageous for cladding materials, a lower mass attenuation coefficient for high-energy photons (over 100 keV) is preferred since it indicates that the material permits higher radiation transparency, which lowers the possibility of gamma-interaction damage.

In Figure 1 and 2, silicon carbide (SiC) absorbs less gamma radiation produced during nuclear fission than zircaloy due to its lower mass attenuation coefficient. In order to maintain the integrity of the cladding over time, this feature allows SiC to endure radiation more effectively without suffering major damage.

In Figure 3 and 4, Zircaloy (E110) consistently shows a lower HVL compared to SiC across the energy range from 0.1 MeV to 20 MeV. A lower HVL means that Zircaloy requires less thickness to reduce gamma radiation intensity by half, indicating better shielding capability than SiC.

In Figure 5 and 6, Zircaloy has a stable Z_{eff} around 40, which remains constant over the entire energy range. SiC has a lower Z_{eff} (~10-12), which is significantly less than that of Zircaloy. A higher Z_{eff} in Zircaloy suggests better gamma radiation interaction capability, enhancing its radiation attenuation properties.

In Figure 7 and 8, Zircaloy has a lower N_{eff} (~ 2.7×10^{23} electrons/g) than SiC (~ 3.0×10^{23} electrons/g) over the whole energy spectrum. Even though SiC has a higher electron density, Zircaloy is the better option for cladding materials because of its higher atomic number, which is more important for effective radiation shielding.

This study provides a comparison between Cr-coated Zircaloy and SiC as cladding materials. Both EpiXS and Geant4 agree well in the investigation of

cladding material selection. Geant4 is a reliable Monte Carlo simulation software for studying the interaction of gamma radiation with materials.

7 Conclusion

Silicon Carbide (SiC) is generally a better material for nuclear fuel cladding in terms of mass attenuation properties. Its lower photon absorption, especially at high energies, combined with its superior mechanical and thermal stability, makes it more suitable for long-term performance in reactor environments. At lower photon energies, zircaloy's greater mass attenuation coefficient allows it to absorb more radiation, particularly by photoelectric absorption. Because zircaloy absorbs more than SiC, it can accelerate material degradation and lead to overheating, making it less suitable for long-term reactor use.

Radiation transparency and resistance to damage from radiation are critical for cladding materials. Cr-coated SiC emerges as an ideal candidate due to its enhanced corrosion resistance, thermal stability, and reduced neutron absorption cross-section. These properties contribute to better stability and performance over time, especially under accident scenarios, further strengthening its role in Accident-Tolerant Fuel (ATF) designs.

The study highlights the importance of Cr-coating in mitigating corrosion and improving mechanical strength, particularly in high-temperature and high-radiation environments. The results from Geant4 simulations validate the superiority of SiC in terms of shielding performance, as evidenced by its lower mass attenuation coefficient and higher thermal resistance compared to Zircaloy. The additional validation using EpiXS further ensures the reliability of the results, with deviations kept within acceptable limits, demonstrating the robustness of the computational framework.

Furthermore, this research emphasizes the potential for integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Computational Intelligence (CI) techniques to enhance modeling precision and predict material performance under complex reactor conditions. Future work can focus on experimental validation and the development of hybrid designs incorporating multi-layered coatings to further optimize safety and efficiency.

Overall, this study establishes Cr-coated SiC as a promising cladding material for next-generation nuclear reactors, offering improved radiation

resistance, thermal performance, and long-term durability. The insights provided lay a foundation for further advancements in nuclear fuel cladding materials, contributing to enhanced reactor safety and performance.

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Contribution of Individual Authors to the Creation of a Scientific Article (Ghostwriting Policy)

Md Minhazul Mostafa led the study’s conception, modeling design, data analysis, manuscript drafting, literature review, resource provision, and writing.

A. S. Mollah provided conceptual input, review, editing, interpretation of results, and supervision. All authors have reviewed the findings and approved the final manuscript version.

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